

Formation of CuCrCoFeNiO High Entropy Alloy Thin Films by rapid thermal processing of Cu/CrNiO/FeCo multilayers

Anni Wang^{1*}, Manuel Oliva-Ramirez¹, Maria Caplovicova², Viliam Vretenar², Julius Boettcher¹, Marcus Hopfeld¹, Thomas Kups¹, Dominik Flock¹, Henry Romanus³, Peter Schaaf¹

¹ TU Ilmenau, Institute of Materials Science and Engineering and Institute of Micro and Nanotechnologies MacroNano®, Chair Materials for Electrical Engineering and Electronics, Gustav-Kirchhoff-Str. 5, 98693 Ilmenau, Germany

² Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia

³ TU Ilmenau, Institute of Micro- and Nanotechnologies MacroNano®, Gustav-Kirchhoff-Straße 7, 98693 Ilmenau, Germany

*E-Mail: Anni Wang; anni.wang@tu-ilmenau.de

Abstract

This study presents the synthesis of High Entropy Alloy (HEA) films starting from elemental Cu and binary alloy CoFe and CrNiO multilayers, followed by rapid thermal processing (RTP). By that, the HEA films (HEAFs) were fabricated by phase formation via short-range and fast diffusion processes. Multilayers with a total thickness of 760 nm consisting of 16 repetitions of a Cu (11 nm)/CrNiO (16.5 nm)/CoFe (20 nm) sequence were annealed at temperatures from 600 °C to 1000°C for 5 minutes. The reaction products were then analyzed by means of X-ray diffraction

(XRD) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) combined with electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS), in order to identify the phase transformations and elemental distributions. A duplex FCC structure containing CrCoFeNiO HEA and pure Cu phase was successfully synthesized at 600 °C and 800 °C by the solid-state reaction. CuCrCoFeNiO HEA formed within in a Cu nanocrystalline matrix. As the annealing temperature increased, the oxygen content in the films decreased, Both HEA and Cu possess significant (111) preferred orientation. The HEA phase demonstrated a typical microstructure of alloys with intensive nano-twins and dislocation pile up. Moreover, the grain growth kinetics of the HEA phase was evaluated, and the activation energy was found to be 185(10) kJ/mol. This is comparable to that of conventional stainless steel (~150 kJ/mol) and less than half of the value for CrCoFeNi bulk (434 kJ/mole). A surface energy-driven grain growth mechanism of the HEAFs is proposed in this study by revisiting the key core effects of HEAs, including entropy effect, severe lattice distortion, and sluggish diffusion.

Graphical Abstract

Keywords: *CuCrCoFeNi0, high entropy alloys thin film (HEAF), High entropy alloys (HEAs), Multilayer, alloying, nanocrystalline HEAs, multilayer alloy formation (MAF), nanometallurgy*

1. Introduction

Multilayer-deposition and subsequent rapid thermal annealing procedures have already been utilized for the formation of MAX phase thin films [1-3], where the nanometallurgy leads to a significant reduction of annealing conditions to form the phase from 1500 °C for several hours to 900 °C for only a few seconds. Therefore, this could be a promising route to produce high entropy alloy thin films (HEAFs). Up to date, only a few studies have reported utilizing a multilayer system for HEAFs synthesis [4-7]. Multilayer HEAFs have been proposed by researchers to modify their mechanical properties [4-6]. There, by stacking BCC-FCC nanolaminate HEAs, the strength and deformability can be enhanced by incorporating nano-twinning and interfacial strengthening mechanisms. Unusual plastic deformation behavior has been observed in Cu/FeCoCrNi, where dislocations could travel through coherent crystalline interfaces and are trapped in HEA layers [5]. In 2019, Cai et al. demonstrated a similar approach to CoCrCuFeNi/Al multilayers and successfully synthesized a dual-phase FCC-BCC HEAF at 550 °C within 1 hour, showing a tunable mechanical property through grain boundary, phase interfacial and solid solution strengthening [7]. It is notable that the synthesis temperature was below the melting temperature of Al and CoCrCuFeNi, and conventional casting and arc melting processes on bulk AlCoCrCuFeNi HEA [8, 9].

Conceivably, diffusion in the thin films is promoted by intense defects, such as vacancies, grain boundaries, interphase boundaries, and surfaces. Therefore, fast intermixing of elements and lower annealing conditions could be achieved [10-12]. For the nanolaminate structure, the

diffusion paths and reactions can be tailored by the nanolayer structure and sequence, respectively. Moreover, the template-texture effect from the as-deposited layers could also create an efficient diffusion channel. Thus, we propose a synthesis method to prepare HEAFs from a multilayer system containing elemental or alloy nanolayers and by a subsequent rapid thermal annealing treatment. This method is an attempt to transfer and simplify the conventional HEA fabrication processes in the nanometer scale and to investigate the competition between kinetic and thermodynamic influence on the HEAFs phase formation behavior. CuCrCoFeNi HEA was selected here because of its well-known mechanical properties and intensive studies on its bulk and thin film forms [13-24]. Cu segregated HEA phase in CuCrCoFeNi bulk HEA were often reported depending on the synthesis route, e.g., supercooling temperature [21], quench rate [13, 17], post-annealing condition [14, 21, 23, 25-27]. Similar to previous investigations on FINEMET [28, 29], an amorphous $\text{Fe}_{73.5}\text{Cu}_1\text{Nb}_3\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9$ alloy, Cu segregation plays a crucial role in transforming amorphous alloys into a nanocrystalline state upon annealing. The more facile crystallization of Cu and diffusion hindering effect for the surrounding Fe-Si matrix resulted in a uniformly distributed nano-crystalline state. The utilization of Cu layers in a HEAFs multilayer synthesis is thus of great interest, and the potential restriction of diffusion process from HEA phases could lead to a formation of nanoparticle Cu that reinforces the mechanical strength of HEAF.

2. Experimental Procedures

Metallic multilayer coatings were deposited via DC magnetron sputtering (LA 440S, Ardenne) employing three cathodes, where Cu (99.99% purity, FHR), CrNiO (about 58 at%Cr, 24 at%Ni, 18 at%O FHR) and CoFe (50 at%Co, 50 at%Fe, FHR) targets were placed. Cathodes

were operated at 200 W DC, and the layer thicknesses were controlled by adjusting the deposition time with precalibrated deposition rates. The layer sequence and thicknesses were modulated as following: Cu (11 nm), CrNiO (16.5 nm), and CoFe (20 nm), as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Schematic view of the deposition and annealing sequence: (a) Onto a sapphire (0001) substrate 11 nm Cu has been deposited, followed by 16.5 nm Cr-NiO and 20 nm CoFe. The deposition sequence was repeated 16 times to reach a total thickness of about 760 nm. (b-d) Structural evolution of the annealed samples from 600 °C, 800 °C to 1000 °C for 5 minutes. Phase formation of CrCoFeNiO HEA was first observed at 600 °C (b), followed by a rapid grain growth of the HEA grains (c and d). At 1000 °C, CuCrCoFeNiO/Cu HEAF was formed. Annealing twins and dislocations are labeled and shown in (b-d).

The layer stacking was prepared for a non-equiatomic Cu-Cr-Co-Fe-Ni HEA, and the ordering CrNiO layers were designed to simulate a surface oxide and corresponding entrainment defect in the conventional casting process. A total of 16 repetitions deposited on $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ c-plane oriented sapphire substrates (sapphire (0001)) with an overall coating thickness of 760 nm. Prior to deposition, the substrate surface was cleaned with acetone and dried by blowing nitrogen gas and then immediately placed into the deposition chamber. Then, the chamber was pumped down to a base pressure of 8×10^{-7} mbar; consequently, high purity Ar (99.9995% in purity) gas was

introduced with a flow rate of 80 sccm to maintain a working pressure at 8.8×10^{-3} mbar. The deposition process was operated at ambient temperature, and no substrate bias was applied. All targets were sputter cleaned for 5 minutes prior to deposition.

Afterward, the as-deposited samples were then annealed using rapid thermal processing RTP (Jetstar 100, Jipelec) in Ar/H₂ protective forming gas at 600 °C, 800 °C, and 1000 °C for 5 minutes; given the sample names by annealing temperature time is always 5 minutes), i.e. 600C, 800C and 1000C. Fig. 2 shows the time-temperature histories of 5 min holding time processing at different maximum temperatures. The RTP chamber was preconditioned by heating to 200 °C for 40 s before the annealing process. The heating rate was controlled to be 6.6 K/s starting from 200 °C, and the cooling rate depends on the holding temperature (5 K/s ~15 K/s).

Figure 2 Time-temperature curves for the specimens annealed for 5 minutes at 600 °C, 800 °C, and 1000 °C. The heating rate is about 6.6 K/s, and the cooling rates are given in the graph for the various annealing temperatures for the regions between the dashed lines. After that, the cooling rate is again approximately the same for all samples at about 0.8 K/s.

The as-deposited and heat-treated specimens were characterized for their microstructure and composition using X-ray diffractometer (XRD), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) combined with electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS), respectively. Siemens D5000 X-ray diffractometer operated at 40 kV and 40 mA with Cu K α X-ray source ($\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$) in Bragg-Brentano θ - 2θ and grazing incident diffraction (GID) geometries was utilized. The diffractometer was under parallel-beam configuration with a line focus, where the size of the beam-defining collimating slit was 1 mm. 2θ scans ranged from 20° to 100° for both θ - 2θ and GID methods, and a sampling step of 0.02° and a rate of $1.2^\circ/\text{min}$ were employed. For the GID scan, the incident angle of 3° was set with the effective penetration depth covering the entire film thickness. Identification of the crystalline phases was conducted using DIFFRAC. EVA V5.1 and Peakfit V4.2 software and coupled with the powder diffraction files (PDF) database [30]. The pseudo-Voigt function was applied for peak position determination and deconvolution of overlapping peaks, and the influence of K α 2 and background were stripped by Rachinger correction and n-th order polynomial fitting before profile fitting. Focused ion beam (FIB) cross-sectional images were accomplished in a dual-beam SEM/FIB system (Auriga 60, Zeiss) to observe the microstructural evolution concerning different thermal treatment before the preparation of TEM lamellas. Ga $^+$ ion beam was utilized in FIB milling, a stepwise ion beam thinning procedure was done to reduce ion damage on the TEM lamella starting from 30 kV and finishing with 5 kV ions. A Lift-out technique was carried out for the TEM specimen preparation. A Cu TEM grid was used. The samples were characterized using TEM (JEM-ARM200cF, Joel) operated under 200 keV and equipped with spherical aberration correctors allowing resolutions of 78 pm in STEM mode and of 110 pm in TEM mode. Elemental analysis was performed utilizing the EELS method avoiding additional Cu

signals from the TEM grid. The grain size was evaluated by using imageJ software on TEM bright and dark field images at various locations to assure a reliable statistical interpretation.

3. Results

3.1 As-deposited state

The as-deposited specimen was analyzed for its microstructure, overall composition, and crystallographic structure of CrNiO, CoFe, and Cu stacking layers by utilizing STEM, EELS, and XRD.

(d)

(e)

Figure 2 STEM images of the as-deposited sample. (a) Annular dark-field (ADF) imaging overview of the TEM lamella, where the selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern is inserted. The SAED pattern was taken from the center of the specimen (marked with the white

circle, $r = 100$ nm) and identified by crystalline structures labeled as BCC ($a = 2.892(10)$ Å), FCC ($a = 3.568(50)$ Å) corresponding to CoFe ($a = 2.762\sim 2.977$ Å [31]), and Cu ($a = 3.615$ Å), CrNiO ($a = 3.585$ Å) phases observed from XRD analysis. (b) bright-field (BF) and (c) ADF images of the microstructure are presented, and the location of CrNiO, CoFe, and Cu layers are labeled. EELS measurements on the as-deposited sample: (d) element mappings and (f) line scans for O, Cr, Ni, Fe, Co, and Cu. The location of the line scan is indicated in (c).

Table 1: Overall elemental concentrations obtained from the EELS results (Fig. 2 (d)) of the as deposited sample. The average compositional data was taken over a selected region in Fig. 2 (d) based on the relative thickness maps where a characteristic layer structure was covered. The uncertainty is about 1-2 at.%.

Element	O	Cr	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu
Overall concentration (at.%)	12.8	16.3	21.6	17.4	13.6	18.4

From the TEM image in Fig. 2 (a), the film thickness was measured to be about $752(10)$ nm consisting of 16 stacking sequences of 47.8 nm each. This is very close to the desired specimen design (47.5 nm). In Figs. 2 (b) and (c), the typical columnar structures were observed in each layer, where the column width is about 15 nm for the Cr-NiO and CoFe layers, and about 12 nm for the Cu layer. The selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern taken from the marked area in part (a) is inserted, where the characteristic diffraction rings for nanocrystalline thin films were observed. Both FCC and BCC crystalline structures can be recognized as labeled. Because of the proximity of the lattice parameters and structures, a rough correlation could be made accordingly: FCC diffraction rings could correspond to Cu and Ni, while the BCC diffraction rings should relate to Cr and CoFe of B2 structure. Further investigation of the crystallographic structure was conducted using XRD.

Fig. 2 (d-e) depicts the EELS compositional in-depth profile of the as-deposited sample. The mappings of O, Cr, Ni, Fe, Co, and Cu are in part (d), and a corresponding line scan along the growth direction from part (c) is in part (e). The overall composition taken from part (d) is listed

in Table 1. The elemental profiles are in accordance with the layer stacking Cu/CoFe/Cr-NO, and a negligible degree of intermixing was observed at Cu-CoFe and Cu-CrNi interfaces with sharp compositional boundaries. On the other hand, a small amount of Cu and Ni (about 4 %) diffused from Cu and Cr-NiO to CoFe layers. This intermixing of Cu and Ni could be a result of ion bombardment and ion channeling effects promoting atoms into the loose BCC structure of CoFe. From the compositional line scan in part (e), the CoFe layers show an equiatomic content, while Cr-NiO layers show a compositional ratio of Cr: Ni: O = 2: 1: 1. The overall composition is sufficient to form a high entropy alloy compound. Because of the presence of oxygen, current phase prediction models could not be applied directly [32-36]. Nevertheless, an attempt was made by considering only Cr, Co Fe, Ni, and Cu, and a solid solution FCC structure was predicted. The results are presented in Table 2. The physiochemical properties used for evaluation are in Table A in the Appendix. . Nonetheless, the formation of HEA or/and high entropy oxide thin film is of great interest in investigating the impact of ordered oxygen layers on mass transportation and HEA phase formation tendency.

Table 2: Phase prediction based on the Cr, Co, Fe, and Ni composition with and without oxygen content of the as-deposited specimen (Table 1) and physicochemical/thermodynamic properties, including the valance electron concentration (VEC), electronegativity difference $\Delta\chi$, atomic size difference (δ), mixing enthalpy (ΔH_{mix}), mixing entropy (ΔS_{mix}), weighting melting temperature ($T_m = \sum c_i(T_m)_i$), and $\Omega = T_m \Delta S_{mix}/|\Delta H_{mix}|$ [32-36]. R is gas constant . $R = 8.3145 \text{ J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$

As-deposited	HEAs Phase determination parameters							Phase
	VEC	$\Delta\chi$	δ (%)	ΔH_{mix} (kJ/mol)	ΔS_{mix} (J/K)	T_m (K)	Ω	
CrCoFeCuNi	8.82	0.09	1.16	3.94	1.60R	1760	5.95	Solid solution (FCC)

CrCoFeCuNiO	8.42	0.21	5.27	-253.1	1.78R	1535	0.09	Possible bulk metallic glass
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Figs. 3 (a) and (b) depict the X-ray diffraction patterns in GID and BB scans of the as-deposited specimen. The assessments of Cr-NiO, Cu and CoFe layers are based on powder diffraction standards (CoFe: PDF 65-4134, Cu: PDF 04-0836, NiO: PDF 04-0835, Ni: PDF 04-0850 and Cr: PDF 06-0694) [30].

(a)

(b)

Figure 3 XRD diffractograms of the as-deposited specimen in (a) grazing incidence (GI) and (b) Bragg-Brentano (BB) geometry. Definitely present phases are indicated with solid lines, others with point-lines. The assessments of Cr-NiO, Cu and CoFe layers are based on powder diffraction standards (CoFe: PDF 65-4134, Cu: PDF 04-0836, NiO: PDF 04-0835, Ni: PDF 04-0850 and Cr: PDF 06-0694) [30].

For the Cr-NiO layers, typical oxides of Cr and Ni were examined, and the phase identification was based on the characteristic diffraction peaks of the prevalent intensities, in particular 43.29° and 37.23° for NiO. In both BB and GI-XRD scans (Figs. 3 (a, b)), no definite trace of crystalline oxides was found, leading to an assumption of amorphous oxides and/or oxygen solid solution within Cr-Ni matrix. Furthermore, neither pure Ni nor pure Cr could be fully identified, and the shift of both Ni and Cr peaks to lower 2θ angles hints the existence of a CrNiO solid solution phase. The lattice parameter is determined to be 3.585 \AA , in accordance with the literature ($a \sim 3.60 \text{ \AA}$) [37, 38], corresponding to the fcc NiCr phase. Thus, the slightly increased lattice parameter in comparison with Cr_2Ni_3 ($a = 3.579 \text{ \AA}$) might imply a substitutional solution of

Cr and O in fcc-Ni, forming a metastable CrNiO fcc solid solution [39]. Nevertheless, the possibility of amorphous CrO_x and NiO_x cannot be precluded. Moreover, Cr-NiO layers show a strongly preferred orientation of (111), as shown in both BB and GI scans in Figs. 3 (a, b), in both of which high intensity of fcc (111) peak was observed.

Cu layers possess comparable lattice parameters of $a_{Cu} = 3.615 \text{ \AA}$ and crystallographic structure as an fcc-CrNiO phase. Consequently, their diffraction patterns are mostly overlapped and problematic to differentiate. Furthermore, the nano-crystalline nature of thin films (Fig. 2) can lead to broadened XRD peaks, hence increasing the difficulties in verifying crystalline Cu and CrNi. As for the CoFe layer, a BCC structure with a lattice parameter of $a=2.891 \text{ \AA}$ with a preferred orientation of (110) is recognized in both GID and BB scans. Bcc (110) peak shows the highest intensity among all other bcc (hkl) peaks. It is common for metallic coatings to develop preferred orientations corresponding to the close-packed planes to reduce the total surface energy in compensating to the volumetric strain energy; for instance, (111) preferred orientation for fcc and (110) for bcc metallic thin films [40, 41]. The microstructure of the as-deposited sample can thus be delineated as a sequential stacking of Cu(fcc)/CoFe(bcc)/CrNiO(fcc) with a parallelism of the close-packed FCC(111) and BCC(110) planes.

3.2 Annealed samples

Fig. 4 compare the XRD patterns of annealed specimens at 600 °C, 800 °C, and 1000 °C with the as-deposited specimen. After heat-treatment above 600°C, the diffraction peaks of CoFe at 44.97° and 82.96° vanished, as shown in Figs. 4 (a, b), meanwhile, new series of Bragg peaks appeared at $2\theta \sim 43^\circ, 51^\circ, 75^\circ, 90^\circ$ and 96° , corresponding to (111), (200), (220), (311) and (200) fcc crystalline planes, comparable to the

literature of FCC HEAs [13, 15, 17, 18, 20, 21, 27, 42, 43]. No typical oxide byproducts of CrCoFeNi-based HEAs, especially Cr_2O_3 , were found in our specimens [44]. The (hkl) planes were labeled in Fig. 4 (a, b). The X-ray patterns mainly comprised of two FCC structures, F1 and F2. The fitted diffraction peaks and calculated lattice parameters of each sample are tabulated in Table 3. Lattice parameters of F1 are close to Cr_2Ni_3 (3.579 Å), fcc Fe (3.571 Å), while those of F2 are closer to fcc Cu (3.615 Å). Both F1 and F2 phases are comparable to CuCrCoFeNi HEAs (3.58 to 3.61 Å) [13, 26, 45]. Similar observations were found in [13, 21, 27] on cast CuCoCrFeNi alloy with a small undercooling range ($\Delta T = 40\sim 80\text{K}$), where two FCC phase-separated due to Cu segregation. Moreover, the annealed films possessed a strong (111) preferential orientation for both F1 and F2 phases. In **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** Fig. 4 (c), (111) and (222) peaks intensities increased as the annealing temperature elevated. The GID scans (Fig. 3 (a)) also detected a resultant uprising (222) in-plane texture in agreement with the BB scans.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4. XRD patterns of as-deposited and annealed specimens at 600 °C, 800 °C, and 1000 °C for 5 minutes using (a) GID and (b) BB scans. The FCC structures of CuCrCoFeNiO was labeled as F1 ($a = 3.577 \text{ \AA}$) and F2 ($a = 3.598 \text{ \AA}$), where the corresponding Bragg's reflection is indicated above. In part (c), the evolution of F1 and F2 phases in (111) and (222) diffraction peaks with respect to annealing temperature are displayed.

Table 3: XRD peaks positions obtained from Fig. 4 for annealed specimens. The diffraction peaks were categorized according to their fcc (hkl) planes, and the corresponding F1 (HEA) and F2 (Cu) phases were labeled behind the 2θ angles. A hyphen is placed when no peak was detected.

XRD Peak (degree)	Sample name					
	600C		800C		1000C	
fcc-(hkl)	BB	GI	BB	GI	BB	GI
111	43.90° (F1) 43.36° (F2)	43.85° (F1) 43.45° (F2)	43.92° (F1) 43.49° (F2)	43.90° (F1) 43.54° (F2)	43.88° (F1) 43.36° (F2)	-
200	-	51.30° (F1) 50.20° (F2)	-	50.71° (F1) 51.36° (F2)	-	-
220	-	75.20° (F1)	-	75.12° (F1)	-	75.08° (F1)

		74.00° (F2)		74.17° (F1)		74.29° (F2)
311	-	91.56° (F1) 90.00° (F2)	-	90.90° (F1) 90.50° (F2)	-	-
222	96.88° (F1) 95.69° (F2)	96.47° (F1) 95.94° (F2)	96.88° (F1) 95.69° (F2)	95.87° (F1) 95.69° (F2)	95.46° (F1) 96.70° (F2)	-
Lattice parameter	$a_{F1(HEA)} = 3.568 \text{ \AA}$ $a_{F2(Cu)} = 3.604 \text{ \AA}$		$a_{F1(HEA)} = 3.584 \text{ \AA}$ $a_{F2(Cu)} = 3.592 \text{ \AA}$		$a_{F1(HEA)} = 3.581 \text{ \AA}$ $a_{F2(Cu)} = 3.598 \text{ \AA}$	

Fig. 5 exhibits the EELS elemental mappings of specimens 600C, 800C, and 1000C, respectively. The EELS compositional profile for 600C (Fig. 5 (a)) shows an intermixing within CrNi, and CoFe layers, and pure Cu layers. CoFe and CrNiO layers functioned as diffusion couple and the diffusion paths can be observed from the opposite (Cr, Ni) and (Co, Fe) concentration gradients in Fig. 5 (b). Oxygen was found only in Cr-Co-Fe-Ni mixture with no transparent concentration gradient within, while Cu averted itself from the oxygen impurity. A compositional ratio of O: Cr: Fe: Co: Ni = 23.68 : 17.8 : 25.3 : 22.9 : 10.4 at % were evaluated from the average of corresponding HEA grains, as illustrated in part (d). Only a small amount of Cr, Co, Fe, Ni, O was found penetrating the Cu grain boundaries up to 5 nm. The Cr, Co, Fe, Ni, and O concentration gradients are mostly contributed from the detection limit and scanning beam size of STEM-EELS measurement, and a mixed composition signal was detected from those neighboring HEA grains. By combining with the observation from the XRD patterns in Figs. 4, the F1 phase is the CrCoFeNiO HEA, and the F2 phase is the remaining Cu layers. It is worth mentioning that the HEA grains have a wide range of component ratios, including CrNi-riched and CoFe-riched HEA phases. Therefore, the HEA XRD pattern (F1) at 600°C could only indicate the formation of fcc solid solution, and the lattice parameter is a weighting sum of HEA component XRD spectra. Nevertheless, a critical temperature at 600 °C for HEA phase formation can be specified.

The composition profiles of 800 °C and 1000 °C specimens are in Figs. 5 (b) and (c), respectively. The distributions of elements are similar to those of the 600 °C sample, consisting of pure Cu and CrCoFeNiO HEA phases. In addition, significant morphology changed from a nanolaminate (600C) to a granular structure (800C and 1000C). In comparison with the HEA phase in the 600C sample, both the line scans of those 800C and 1000C samples presented a homogeneous element distribution inside those HEA grains. These results signify a temperature-dependent interdiffusion between CrNiO and CoFe layers; and starting from 800 °C, a complete intermixing of CrCoFeNiO can be reached. The mean concentration of the HEA phase of each sample was collected and plotted in part (d). As the annealing temperature increased from 600 °C to 1000 °C, the oxygen content decreased from 23.7 to 7.7 at%. Meanwhile, Cr, Fe, and Ni increased. In the 1000C sample with the lowest oxygen content (7.7 at%), Cu of 2.9 at% was incorporated into the HEAs phase, forming CuCrCoFeNiO/Cu HEAF.

(a) 600C

(b) 800C

(c) 1000C

(d)

Figure 5 EELS element mapping and line scan of the (a) 600C, (b) 800C, and (c) 1000C samples. The high surface oxygen concentration in 1000C is probably an artifact due to the weak signal on a crack between the thin film and carbon-Pt layers. The line scan region and its direction are labeled by a white arrow line in the corresponding TEM-BF image. (d) Mean concentrations of CrCoFeNiO calculated from the EELS line scan results for the sample annealed at 600 °C (calculated from 0 to 14 nm, 22 nm to 45 nm, and 59 to 68 nm) 800 °C (calculated from position 50 nm to 200 nm) and 1000 °C for 5 minutes (calculated from position 0 nm to 400 nm).

Microstructure evolution was investigated by utilizing STEM in Figs. 6-8 for the samples 600C, 800C and 1000C, respectively. Fig. 6 shows the 600C specimen. A grain size of 32(8) nm within the CoFe-CrNiO layers can be seen in both bright- and dark-field images correspondingly in (a) and (b). These grains are the CrCoFeNiO HEA, revealing from the EELS (Fig. 5(a)) mapping. The SAED pattern in Fig 6 (c) shows fcc structure with the fitting of diffraction ring labeled as (111), (002), (022), and (113), akin to the diffraction pattern from XRD in Figs. 4 (a, b). The lattice

constant was calculated to be 3.549 Å identical to the CrCoFeNiO phase ($a = 3.568$ Å) in Table B. The SAED pattern contributes mostly from the CoCrFeNiO HEA than Cu (3.604 Å) layers, which could be owing to a better crystallinity of CoCrFeNiO. In search of crystalline Cu, nano-scaled grains of ~5nm were observed in Fig. 6(d). This can point out the weak signal of Cu phases in XRD patterns in the 600C specimen in Figs. 4 (a, b). Intensive amount of inclined annealing nano-twins penetrated across Cu/CoCrFeNiO interfaces, as shown in parts (e), and the $\Sigma 3$ {111} twins, were recognized through FFT images at twin boundary as revealed in the insert in part (f). The twin distance was about 7 nm.

As the annealing temperature increased to 800°C (Fig. 7), instead of the multilayer structure, the CoCrFeNiO HEA phase with an enlarged grain size of 154(57) nm was surrounded by Cu matrix (Fig. 7 (a, b)). The Cu and HEA interfaces in Fig. 7 (a) were identified through EELS mapping. Figs. 7 (a) and (b) show localized dislocation piled up in HEAs grains; crossing Cu/HEA boundaries a decrease of dislocation distance and eventually vanished in Cu grain. This unusual dislocation behavior was observed recently in [5] on a Cu/CoCrNiFe HEAF, where the HEA phase and Cu phase function as a dislocation acceptor and donor. The annealing twins were found only in HEAs grains in accompanying with twin distance of 30 nm (Figs. 7 (c)); moreover, the twin boundaries were mostly parallel to the sample surface normal is aligned with the (111) preferred orientation (Fig. 4 (c)). In between HEAs grains (Fig. 6 (d)), nano-crystalline Cu was also observed as in 600C specimen.

Fig. 8 exhibits the STEM images of the 1000C specimen. Large HEA grains of 621(121) nm occupied the entire film thickness (760 nm), while the pure Cu nanocrystalline phase continuously distributed between HEA grains. Reduced annealing twin density and increased twin distance to 90 nm can be perceived in Figs. 8 (a-c). Two distinct HEA grain boundaries were observed in part

(d) and (e). In Fig. 8 (d), nanocrystalline Cu (~10 nm) as solute segregated at HEA grain boundaries, whereas a low-angle grain boundary without Cu segregation in Fig. 8(e) with characteristic dislocations array. Owing to the rapid grain growth of HEAs and suppressed diffusion of Cu phase, the remaining Cu traps along the grain boundaries, forming a continuous nanocrystalline cluster. This morphology is similar to the segregation of Cu in CuCrCoFeNi HEAs [13].

Figure 6 STEM images of the 600C sample. (a) Bright-field (BF) and (b) Annular dark-field (ADF) imaging overview of the TEM lamella. The selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern is shown in (c). The SAED pattern was identified as FCC (hkl) planes with a lattice constant of $a = 3.549 \text{ \AA}$, comparable to lattice parameter of CrCoFeNi ($a = 3.572 \text{ \AA}$). (d) ADF image taken from the Cu layer. (e) Ultrascan images consisting of annealing twins crossing HEAs and Cu layers, and (f) local images of the twin boundary and FFT insert taken from the marked area.

Figure 7 STEM images of the 800C sample. (a) Bright-field (BF) and (b) Annular dark-field (ADF) imaging overview of the TEM lamella. (c) ADF images focused on annealing twins. (d) ADF image is taken from the annealing twin boundary from (c). (e) BF images at the Cu segregation at HEAs grain boundaries.

Figure 8 STEM images of the 1000C sample. (a) Bright-field (BF) and (b) Annular dark-field (ADF) imaging overview of the TEM lamella. (c) DF and BF combining image of a twin. (d) Cu segregated at HEA grain boundary, inserts shows the nano-crystalline Cu grains. (e) Ultra scan at grain boundaries between CrCoFeNi HEA phases, where low-angle grain boundary with arranged dislocations was observed. (f) BF ultra scan image of the substrate (Al_2O_3) and HEA grain and the insert is the FFT taken from the HEA area, and the lattice constant and zone axis were measured to be 3.523 \AA and $(1 -1 2)$, respectively.

4. Discussion

In this study, a composite HEAF consisting of CrCoFeNiO HEA and pure Cu was synthesized using a multilayer alloying formation method at different annealing temperatures from 600 to 1000 °C. The annealing temperature is 300 to 1000 °C lower than the bulk metal and alloy melting temperature as listed in Table A. Even with the consideration of melting temperature decrease in nanoscale materials [46], the CrNiO and CoFe phases should remain in the solid-state for most annealing conditions, in particular at 600 °C. On the other hand, Cu with the lowest melting point could be liquid form. Cu with a grain size of 35 nm was reported to reduce the melting temperature to 177 °C (450 K) [47]. Besides, the TEM morphologies (Figs. 7 and 8) show a similar microstructural change as liquid phase sintering for copper steels (Fe-Cu-C) [48, 49], where a network of liquefied Cu penetrates along the HEA grain boundaries. The liquid-solid Cu-HEA interface should promote a fast interdiffusion and adding more configurational entropy in the formerly formed HEA phase. Thus, it must be thermodynamically favorable to form CuCrCoFeNiO HEA. In addition, the sluggish diffusion effect [50] and high entropy grain boundary effect [51, 52] should restrain mass transportation between CrCoFeNiO grains; therefore, grain growth should be limited. Still, opposite trends were observed against those assumptions: low solubility of Cu in the HEA phase, and rapid grain growth of HEA in comparison with nanocrystalline Cu. Moreover, the Cu matrix indicates a hindering diffusion effect from the HEA surrounding that is similar to our previous investigation on FINEMET [28, 29].

Furthermore, as the annealing temperature increased where oxygen content decreased, the solubility of Cu in HEAs increased from 0 to 2.9 at %— Comparing our results to other literature on CuCrCoFeNi [27, 53, 54], pure Cu segregation and extreme low Cu solubility has not yet been reported. No oxide byproducts of CrCoFeNiO or Cu were found in the annealed specimens [44],

and no indication of high entropy oxide despite the high oxygen content up to 20%. Moreover, the STEM images show typical morphologies of HEAs with intensive annealing twinning and dislocation pile up. CrCoFeNi is known to have excellent oxidation resistance and could tolerate severe oxygen environment without oxidation and degradation up to 800°C; thereby, the oxygen content (7.7 to 23.7 at%) in these annealed samples could be stable in CrCoFeNiO solid solution and not yet reach the border to initiate oxide formation.

Two critical questions, thus should be discussed. First, how does oxygen content impact the HEA phase formation? Second, what is the possible mechanism for rapid grain growth in HEAF?

4.1 Oxygen stabilized entropy effect in HEAs

Owing to the presence of oxygen impurity, current phase prediction models based on HEAs are problematic [32-36]. When including oxygen in the phase determination parameters (Table 2), the increase of mixing enthalpy (ΔH_{mix}) and lattice distortion (δ), along with the significant decrease of $\Omega = \Delta H_{\text{mix}}/T_m\Delta S$ indicate that the specimen should be amorphous metallic glass, which does not match with our results. FCC CrCoFeNiO HEA crystalline structure was observed. Furthermore, the low $\Omega < 1$ implies the effect of configurational entropy is not a dominating factor for phase formation and should not be regarded as HEAs. In this regard, the formation CrCoFeNiO HEA phase without intermetallic compounds and oxide byproducts cannot be explained.

The significant contribution of enthalpy and non-configurational entropy to the phase stability of HEAs has been reported [55]. More recent studies on high entropy oxides (HEOs) [56, 57] have suggested oxygen ion can adequately accommodate the HEA's lattice distortion and thus stabilized the solid solution phase through introducing excess entropy term. The oxygen ions situate steadily in an fcc sub-lattice, where metal cations distribute randomly and homogeneously. It is, therefore,

necessary to include excess entropy terms coming from atomic vibration, magnetic moments as well as electronic effects. All of which could be heavily influenced by the oxygen ions.

Nevertheless, the oxygen content could as well impact the formation of the two separated phases in this study, CrCoFeNiO, and pure Cu. Considering the standard free energies for oxide formation of each element, the highly negative Gibb's free energy of Cr, Co, and Ni in comparison with Cu can be observed in the Ellingham diagram (Fig. A) at the respective annealing temperature (800°C to 1000°C). This implies that the oxygen atoms prone to bonded chemically with Cr, Ni, Co, and Fe and thus prohibits oxygen diffusion into Cu layers. After the CrCoFeNi HEA emerging, Gibb's free energy ($\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$) can be further reduced by the entropy terms (ΔS), resulting in a thermodynamic favor for oxygen atoms to imprison in HEAs phase, and eventually protecting Cu from oxidation. Also, the relative positive binary mixing enthalpies of Cu ($\Delta H_{\text{Cu-x=Cr, Co, Fe, Ni}}$ in Table A) shows less potential to alloy with the HEAs phase. Nonetheless, the influence of oxygen impurity requires further investigation and theoretical models to identify the critical thermodynamic and kinetic aspects for HEA phase formation.

4.2 Grain growth mechanism in HEAFs

Seemly, significant grain growth occurred in our CuCrCoFeNiO HEAFs (Figs. 6-8). The CrCoFeNiO HEA grains grew from 32(8) nm, 155(57) nm to 621(121) nm correspondingly at 600 °C, 800 °C, and 1000 °C for 5 minutes. The grain growth mechanism can be evaluated by applying classic kinetic grain growth theory [58],

$$\ln\left(\frac{d^{1/n}}{t}\right) = \ln k = \ln k_0 - \left(\frac{Q_G}{RT}\right) \quad (1)$$

, where d is the mean grain size of the crystallized alloys annealed at temperature T for time t , d is the grain size, n is the grain growth exponent ($n = 0.3694$ for CrCoFeNi [50]), R is gas constant, and the activation energy (Q_G), k and k_0 are pre-exponential constants. Deducing from the above equations, the Q_G can be obtained from the slope ($\frac{Q_G}{R}$) of the linear fitting of $\ln\left(\frac{d^{1/n}}{t}\right)$ vs. $\frac{1}{T}$ as shows in Fig. 9. Scales of d , t and T are nm, second, and K, respectively. The linear regression fitting of the data yields $Q_0/R = -22200(1221)$. The calculated Q_G for HEA grains in this study is, therefore, 185(10) kJ/mole, and it is akin to those conventional stainless steel (~150 kJ/mole) and less than half of the CrCoFeNi bulk (434 kJ/mole) [50].

For thin film and coatings, surface energy (γ) is the main driving force for grain growth, where the minimization of strain energy (ΔG_s) is dominated by the surface energy term ($\sum d\gamma A$). Thereby, the facets possessed the lowest γ to remain during grain growth, forming a strong preferential texture orientation. This phenomenon can also be applied to the rearrangement of $\Sigma 3$ {111} twins. Similar observations in magnetron sputtered HEAFs, and other alloys coatings are in [13] and [40, 41], respectively. The evolution of (111) preferred orientation in this study demonstrates a typical surface-energy driven growth mechanism that dictates the growth mechanism. Up to now, there are no sufficient experiments or models to elucidate the entropy effect on surface energy and grain growth mechanism in HEAFs.

Here, we reexamine the critical core effects of HEAs on their thin-film form (HEAFs), and the corresponding influence on grain growth in HEAFs, specifically entropy, lattice distortion, and sluggish diffusion effects.

First, the increase of configurational entropy (ΔS) must decrease the surface energy decreases following by $S^S = -\left(\frac{d\gamma}{dT}\right)$. The high-entropy grain boundary effect was proposed by Zhou et al.

on nanocrystalline HEAs [51, 52], and it was considered to be thermodynamic stabilized effect to prevent grain coarsening. However, when considering the kinetic effect on thin-film materials, the high-entropy grain boundary could lead to a fast diffusion, opposite to the sluggish kinetic. In this sense, the low surface energy terms ($\sum d\gamma A$) should lead to facilitate minimization of the surface area. Also, the surface energy anisotropy within the HEA's crystalline structure provides selectivity in the driving force for the growth of secondary grains [59], in particular (111) preferred orientation for fcc structure. Second, the severe lattice distortion as a result of the various atomic size of the elements in HEAs crystal lattice could be relaxed locally at the grain boundaries and surfaces accordingly through accommodating defects and reconstruction of the surface atoms to an equilibrium position. Thereby, the sluggish diffusion owing to lattice distortion at those regions should be alleviated. Combining with the thin film structure of large surface to volume ratio, the severity of both lattice distortion and sluggish diffusion could be lessened in general. Lastly, the importance of sluggish lattice diffusion in HEAFs should be reconsidered since the diffusion mechanism in thin films is a comparative mechanism, involving not only lattice diffusion but also grain boundary and surface diffusions [60]. For typical metal films, grain-boundary diffusion dominates at all practical temperatures due to its higher diffusivities in comparison with lattice one [61]. For HEAFs, this mechanism should be applicable, but with lower diffusivity due to the sluggish kinetic effect and high-entropy grain boundary. It is, thus, reasonable to assume that the rapid grain growth/ coarsening in this study of CrCoFeNiO could be governed by an accelerated diffusion at the grain boundary and driven by the low high entropy surface energy. Still, the roles of the nano-crystalline Cu matrix is unclear.

Meta-stability in HEAFs and nanocrystalline HEAs is not fully understood. The intensive non-equilibrium concentration of vacancies and defects during thin film condensation should

contribute significantly to structural instability. Several ab-initio calculations investigations on CrCoFeNi [62-64] have shown that a high vacancy formation entropy and a wide range of vacancy formation enthalpies of each element. Adding the excess free energy in HEAFs, such as surface energy, strain energy, excessive vacancy concentration, defects, and impurities, the kinetic of vacancy diffusion is thus complex and certainly has a substantial impact on the mass transport mechanism. Nevertheless, more sophisticated and comprehensive grain growth kinetic investigations on the structural and compositional meta-stability in HEAFs are required in developing nano-crystalline HEAs and HEAFs for future applications.

Figure. 9 Grain growth kinetic constant $\ln(d^{1/n}/t)$ as a function of the reciprocal absolute temperature for HEAs, the n value is taken from [50]. d, t and T are grain size (nm), annealing time (s) and temperature (K).

Conclusions

A new multilayer alloy formation method for HEAFs was proposed in this study. A duplex FCC structure containing CrCoFeNiO HEA and Cu phases was successfully synthesized and characterized via XRD, SEM, STEM, and EELS techniques. A schematic view of the composition and structural evolution concerning the annealing temperature is illustrated in Fig. 1. The formation CrCoFeNiO HEA initiated at 600°C and followed by rapid grain growth. The oxygen content decreased as the temperature increased in accompany with a small amount of Cu into CrCoFeNiO. The oxygen content is crucial in HEA phase formation due to the oxygen stabilized entropy terms. A microstructure evolution from nanolaminate to granular structured HEAF was observed, and nanotwin and dislocation were found similar to other literature. The rapid grain growth of the HEAs phase was investigated, and the grain growth activation energy was calculated to be 186(10) KJ/mole comparable to regular stainless steel.

Conflict of interest

We declare that we do not have any commercial or associative interest that represents a conflict of interest in connection with the work submitted.

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Appendix

Table A: Physiochemical properties of Fe, Cr, Cu, Ni, Co and O elements and mixing enthalpies of binary systems containing these elements calculated by Miedema's model [65]. Parameters taken from [65] for Co, Cr, Cu, Fe and Ni. Standard mixing enthalpies of CuO, Fe₃O₄, Ni₂O₃, Co₂O₃ and Cr₂O₃ were used in this table and referred from CRC handbook of Chemistry and Physics [66].

Element	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Ni	O	
Atomic Radius (Å)	1.251	1.249	1.278	1.241	1.246	0.730	
Pauling electronegativity	1.88	1.66	1.90	1.83	1.91	3.44	
Valence electron concentration	9	6	11	8	10	6	
T_m (K)	1768	2130	1356	1808	1728	54	
Mixing enthalpies ΔH (kJ/mol)	Co	-	-4	6	-1	0	-237
	Cr	-	-	12	-1	-7	-1139
	Cu	-	-	-	13	4	-157
	Fe	-	-	-	-	-2	-824
	Ni	-	-	-	-	-	-489
	O						-

Figure. A Ellingham diagram for the formation of oxides based on their standard free energy of formation over temperature [67]. The annealing temperature range is marked by a solid red line .

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